

Analytical Applications of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea. Part VII Gravimetric Determination of Tellurium*

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A new gravimetric method, based on reduction of tellurites and tellurates to elementary tellurium in 3*N*-HCl solutions by amidinothiourea and hydrazine, has been developed. Au (III) is separated from tellurium by extraction with diethyl ether in 1.6 *M*-HCl. Hg (II), Cu (II), and Ag (I) are masked with potassium iodide, thiourea, and HCl, respectively. Other cations and anions have been found not to interfere. Accuracy and relative standard deviation are $\pm 0.3\%$ and $\pm 0.22\%$, respectively.

Amidinothiourea has been used in this laboratory for the estimation of various elements¹. In an earlier communication², a gravimetric method for separation of selenium from tellurium with amidinothiourea was described. The present communication reports the results of a detailed study of gravimetric determination of tellurium with the same reagent.

Except a method by Browning and Flint³, modified by Cheng⁴, involving estimation of tellurium as TeO₂, all the methods for determination of tellurium are based on reduction of tellurite to elementary tellurium. Sulphur dioxide and hydrazine⁵ or hydroxylamine hydrochloride⁶, thiourea⁷, hydriodic acid and sulphur dioxide⁸, and hydrosulphurous acid⁹⁻¹⁰ are some of the common reducing agents used. Among less important are the reducing agents like¹¹ potassium iodide, stannous chloride, titanous chloride, phosphorus and hypophosphorus acids, glucose¹²⁻¹³, and metals like zinc or aluminium. But these reducing agents produce elementary tellurium contaminated with the reaction products. Gold (III) always accompanies tellurium with most, if not all, reducing agents. Palladium (II) is carried down as a telluride whenever elementary tellurium is precipitated in its presence.

Formation of elementary tellurium by the reduction of tellurites and tellurates in HCl medium with amidinothiourea and hydrazine or hydroxylamine hydrochloride has been utilised in the present investigation for the estimation of tellurium.

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EXPERIMENTAL

A. R. grade reagents were used whenever available. The solutions of telluric acid were prepared by dissolving AnalaR $H_2TeO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ in double-distilled water and the strength of the solution was determined by estimating tellurium with sulphur dioxide and hydroxylamine hydrochloride¹⁴.

Interference due to a number of cations and anions was studied by addition of solutions of appropriate salts. Concentrations of these cations and anions present in the test solutions were determined by standard procedures¹⁴. 1-Amidino-2-thiourea was prepared as described earlier¹. A 2% aqueous solution of the reagent was used for precipitating tellurium.

Determination of Tellurium.—To a hot solution of tellurate in HCl excess of 2% amidinothiourea solution and hydrazine or hydroxylamine hydrochloride were added, maintaining the acidity of the final solution at least 3N with respect to HCl. Black precipitates of tellurium slowly appeared. The solution was heated till the precipitates of tellurium were coagulated. These were filtered, washed with hot water, followed with EtOH, dried at 105°, and weighed as elementary tellurium.

TABLE I

Determination of tellurium with amidinothiourea.

Normality of HCl.	Tellurium.		%Error.	Remarks.
	Present.	Found.		
1.0	55.80 mg.	55.00 mg.	-1.40	Incomplete precipitation.
2.0 ..	55.80	55.50	-0.54	Slow ..
3.0	55.80	55.70	-0.18	Complete ..
4.0	55.80	55.90	+0.18	Do
6.0	55.80	55.60	-0.30	Do
4.0	6.38	6.400	+0.33	
..	49.01	49.08	+0.14	
..	64.20	64.20	±0.00	
..	71.60	71.50	-0.10	
..	102.70	102.70	±0.00	
..	128.40	128.10	-0.23	
..	192.60	192.60	±0.00	
..	321.00	321.90	+0.28	
..	386.20	386.90	+0.28	

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TABLE II

Determination of tellurium in presence of other cations.

Cation added.	Tellurium.		%Error.	Cation added.	Tellurium.		%Error.		
	Present.	Found.			Present.	Found.			
Ni ²⁺	603.3 mg.	71.50 mg.	71.41 mg.	-0.12	UO ²⁺	810.3 mg.	71.50 mg.	71.45 mg.	-0.07
Co ²⁺	589.3	71.50	71.46	-0.06	VO ²⁺	669.5	71.50	71.32	-0.25
Th ⁴⁺	232.1	71.50	71.62	+0.17	Tl ³⁺	465.0	71.50	71.50	+0.12
Ce ³⁺	280.3	71.50	71.41	-0.12	Cd ²⁺	562.2	71.50	71.41	-0.12
Zn ²⁺	653.2	71.50	71.38	-0.17	Sb ³⁺	608.8	71.50	71.62	+0.17
Mn ²⁺	549.3	71.50	71.62	+0.17	Bi ³⁺	627.0	71.50	71.34	-0.20
Fe ³⁺	598.0	71.50	71.67	+0.24	Pb ²⁺	414.4	71.50	71.51	+0.02
Al ³⁺	289.7	71.50	71.43	-0.10	Sn ²⁺	593.6	71.50	71.59	+0.12
Cr ³⁺	520.5	71.50	71.67	+0.24	Pd ²⁺	120.2	59.53	59.62	+0.15
					Rh ³⁺	75.8	63.50	63.71	+0.30

TABLE III

Determination of tellurium in presence of Hg, Cu, Ag, and Au.

Tellurium Present.	Tellurium Found.	%Error.	Cation added.	Amount of cation.	Complexing agent added.
59.53	59.45	-0.13	Hg ²⁺	671.4	"
59.53	59.48	-0.09	Cu ²⁺	317.7	Thiourea
59.53	59.63	+0.17	Cu ²⁺	1588.5	"
59.53	59.45	-0.13	Ag ⁺	107.0	HCl
59.53	59.46	-0.12	Ag ⁺	530.4	"
127.8	127.60	-0.16	Au ³⁺	75.0	Removed with
63.90	63.70	-0.30	Au ³⁺	100.0	ether

DISCUSSION

Tellurite is reduced in cold hydrochloric acid solution by amidinothiourea alone, but reduction of tellurate to elementary tellurium with this reagent requires hydrazine or hydroxylamine hydrochloride. For complete precipitation of tellurium, the hydrochloric acid concentration of the solution should be at least 3*N*. At lower acidities precipitation of tellurium is slow and incomplete with consequent low results, as can be seen in Table I. As the precipitation of tellurium does not take place in cold, amidinothiourea solution should preferably be added to a boiling solution of tellurate so that the precipitated tellurium is immediately coagulated.

Interference Studies.—Na₂EDTA and the following anions do not interfere in the estimation of tellurium: halides, sulphate, sulphite, sulphocyanide, nitrite, nitrate, phosphate, pyrophosphate, borate, molybdate, vanadate, citrate, arsenate, tartrate, cyanide, and oxalate. Table II records the cations which do not interfere in the

estimation. The noninterference of rhodium(III) in the estimation of tellurium is of particular interest for the separation of tellurium from rhodium in fission products¹⁵. Silver (I), mercury(II), and copper(II), which provide silver chloride, mercuric sulphide¹, and Cu(ATU)₂ with amidinothiourea in hydrochloric acid solution, are complexed with HCl, KI, and thiourea, respectively (Table III).

Separation of Au(III) from Tellurium.—Au(III), which was coprecipitated with tellurium, was removed by solvent extraction^{16,17} prior to the estimation of tellurium. A mixture of Te(VI) and Au(III) was made 1.5 M with respect to HCl and shaken twice with equal volume of ether in a separating funnel. Au(III) was quantitatively extracted into the organic phase and tellurium remaining in the aqueous phase could be estimated by the proposed method (Table III).

The separation of tellurium from selenium and its subsequent determination have already been described in an earlier paper⁸.

Precision and Accuracy of the Method.—It can be concluded from the results in Table I that in the concentration range of 49.01 to 385.2 mg. of tellurium in 100 ml of the test solution, the accuracy of the present method is better than $\pm 0.3\%$. The variance and the standard deviation are ± 0.076 and ± 0.28 mg. respectively for 127.8 mg. of tellurium. The average of ten determinations with 127.8 mg. of tellurium varies between 127.9 and 127.5 mg. at 95% confidence limits. The confidence limits for the means were calculated¹⁸ from the data as $\pm (ts)/\sqrt{n}$, where n is the number of determinations included in the average, s is the standard deviation, and t is the usual value derived from t -distribution for 95% confidence and $(n-1)$ degrees of freedom.

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